

A Complementary Methodology to Assess Time Management Behaviors

Abstract

Managing time effectively requires making decisions to plan the order of execution of different tasks, so that the maximum gain is achieved in a given period. We designed a test called My Schedule to assess time management, and we report a study of its psychometric properties. We administered My Schedule along with two other objective tests, one that measures time management behaviors (Planning test) and another that assesses risk-tendency (Betting Dice test) to study convergent and divergent validity. In addition, we administered a self-report that assesses time management (TMBQ). My Schedule showed high reliability and moderate convergence with the Planning test and no significant correlation with the Betting Dice test and the TMBQ. Theoretical and practical implications are discussed.

Keywords: time management, assessment, objective test, self-report, computerized testing

My Schedule: A Complementary Methodology to Assess Time Management

Time management skills promote optimal results both in the academic context and at work. Students need to learn to complete course assignments on time, as most academic subjects have a number of deadlines that have to be met in order for the students to pass (Claessens et al., 2007). Some authors have pointed out that effective time management may lead to better academic results (e.g., Britton & Tesser, 1991; Macan et al., 1990). The students will eventually be faced with the need to manage their time in the workplace. For some jobs, especially those that offer flexible working hours or teleworking, time management behaviors are highly important (Orlikowsky & Yates, 2002). Efficient time management behaviors may lead to a better job performance and increased worker satisfaction (e.g., Claessens et al., 2009). As a result, many companies and universities promote time management training programs, sometimes without having adequately evaluated which participants actually need them (Green & Skinner, 2005).

The number of instruments available to assess time management is limited. Many of these instruments have not been developed on the basis of an explicitly described theoretical framework (Hellsten, 2012). The most commonly used instruments for measuring time management are self-reports (Hellsten, 2012). These instruments allow information to be collected quickly but also suffer from limitations such as limited accuracy and bias effects (Ortner & Proyer, 2015). Therefore, several researchers have emphasized the need to develop objective tests as a complementary measure to assess time management (e.g., Jex & Elacqua, 1999; Macan, 1994).

For the present study, we have designed an objective test called My Schedule to assess time management behaviors. Its design is based on one of the theories that has gained the most ground in recent years in the time management literature: the behavioral-decision

making theory (Koch & Kleinman, 2002). The aim of our work is to study the psychometric properties of the My Schedule objective test.

Time Management: Definition and Theoretical Framework

The concept of time management became popular in the 1960s, when it was suggested that time management programs might have positive effects in the workplace (Claessens et al., 2009). Two influential figures in the time management literature are Alan Lakein and Therese H. Macan. Lakein (1973) described time management as a process that implies establishing goals and prioritizing and planning tasks in order to achieve these goals. He used a theoretical analysis of the problem to make recommendations on how to improve time management. Macan (1994) proposed a model in which she described time management as being based on three dimensions (three types of behaviors): setting goals and priorities, establishing mechanisms of time management, and preferences for organization. This model received only partial empirical support (e.g., Adams & Jex, 1997; Jex & Elacqua, 1999).

Despite the wide use of the concept of time management, Claessens and her colleagues noted that there was no generally agreed-upon definition. In 2007, they proposed a definition based on a thorough review of the literature, namely that time management is comprised of “behaviours that aim at achieving an effective use of time while performing certain goal-directed activities” (Claessens et al., 2007, p. 262). Claessens et al. (2009) classify these behaviors as aligning with the following dimensions: time assessment behaviors, monitoring behaviors, planning behaviors and executive behaviors. Their model has received partial empirical support (McNamara, 2016).

In recent years, behavioral decision-making theory (Koch & Kleinman, 2002) has become one of the most important theoretical applications to time management research (Sevary & Kandy, 2011). Koch and Kleinman (2002) demonstrated how time management can be interpreted from the point of view of behavioral decision-making theory. When people

want to achieve a goal, they need to make decisions about which tasks to do and in which order. People can also make decisions to promote the achievement of the goals, for example, by increasing or decreasing the speed or limiting interruptions. In addition, people need to make decisions regarding the environment, which implies minimizing distractions. When making a decision, they need to consider the benefits (e.g., what they obtain if they finish a task) and the costs (e.g., the time and effort they need to spend completing the task, as well as the activities that they will not be able to complete by choosing one task over another). This allows them to estimate the utility or value of a specific choice. Koch and Kleinman argued that it is possible to manage time only if there are competing tasks to do. Efficient time management requires making the optimal choices and prioritizing tasks that offer a high value or that waste less time.

Koch and Kleinman (2002) explain that people who have time management problems are those who perform tasks with a small value rather than those with a high value. Usually this occurs when the tasks with small value can be completed in the short term.

The behavioral-decision making theory has received empirical support, for example by König and Kleinman (2006), who found that people who consider immediate options with less value instead of future options with higher value tend to show fewer time management behaviors. Experimental studies have also provided support for this theory (e.g., Fagerstrøm et al., 2016; Häfner et al., 2014; König & Kleinman, 2007).

Assessing Time Management

Time management behaviors are most commonly measured using self-reports. This methodology provides descriptive information that participants offer about their own behavior. The most frequently used self-report instruments in this area are the Time Management Behavior Questionnaire (TMBQ; Macan et al., 1990), the Time Structure Questionnaire (TSQ; Bond & Feather, 1988), and the Time Management Questionnaire

(Britton & Tesser, 1991). They show acceptable levels of reliability and allow researchers to obtain data quickly, but they also have some limitations. For example, participants might not know how to respond to certain items, as they might not have an accurate self-view of their own motivations and decision criteria. Biases can also affect self-reports. For example, social desirability can influence participants' responses, as they might want to present themselves in a favorable way (Edwards, 1957; McDonald, 2008; Ortner & Proyer, 2015).

Another method to assess time management uses observational checklists: a list of behaviors that can be registered by an observer. For example, DiPipi-Hoy et al. (2009) designed an observational checklist to study the effects of time management training in participants with intellectual disabilities. Observational checklists are less subjective than questionnaires. However, they require long observer training and efforts to reduce the usual reactivity of participants to the presence of an observer (McDonald, 2008).

Researchers that study time management emphasize the need for objective measures to complement data obtained from other methods (e.g., Jex & Elacqua, 1999; Macan, 1994), as suggested by previous researchers such as Raymond B. Cattell and Francis W. Warburton. These authors have significantly promoted the use of objective tests to assess psychological variables (e.g., Cattell & Warbuton, 1967). Objective tests present situations in which participants have to perform tasks that include mechanical or electronic means of registering data on-line and automatically (Santacreu & Hernández, 2017).

Objective tests can be employed as a complementary methodology to assess time management. We found a few objective tests that provide measures of time management behaviors. For example, Tulga and Sheridan (1980) designed a basic computerized objective test in which participants had to obtain points by completing tasks represented by blocks that appeared randomly. They had to select a block to “work” on before a deadline. Participants

could not work on different blocks at the same time. The time management score was the total number of points obtained.

On the other hand, Gongsook (2016) designed a computerized objective test called “Timo’s adventure”. It has some mini-games that assess time perception in children from 4 to 7 years old. Its principal aim is to assess children with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), as they often have problems estimating time intervals (Barkley et al., 2001). For example, in one of the scenarios presented, participants have to inflate a balloon during 10 seconds.

Another objective test was designed by Santacreu (2004a). The test is called the Planning test and assesses time management behaviors of air controllers. It presents three dots that move at different speeds at the top of the screen. At the bottom of the screen there is a funnel. The direction of the dots can be modified by clicking on arrows. Participants that manage to direct the dots to the funnel in the shortest time receive higher scores.

Tulga & Sheridan’s task, Timo’s adventure and the Planning test record data automatically and provide behavioral measures of time management. However, they are not explicitly based on any theoretical analysis of time management behaviors.

In this work, we have designed the My Schedule objective test as a complementary instrument to assess time management and to overcome the limitations of the previous methods described. It presents a schedule page with office activities (e.g., reading emails, working on a computer, attending a meeting, downloading documents) of different values (as they have different importance represented by points and different costs in terms of the time they require to be completed). As will be described in the method section, the value of the activities can be higher if they are completed in specific periods, and the time an activity takes to complete can be reduced. In addition, one of the tasks (downloading documents) can be completed at the same time as others. Participants obtain points when completing tasks. As

derived from the behavioral-decision making theory (Koch & Kleinman, 2002), participants have to make optimal decisions to obtain a large number of points. They have to select the activities that provide the higher value in a specific period.

The test provides added value compared to other methodologies that measure time management. First, the test construction was guided by the behavioral decision-making theory, which is one of the most important theories in time management, supported by a growing empirical support. Secondly, it registers behavioral data, instead of the verbal descriptions about the behavior that self-reports record. Objective tests are more difficult to fake and are less affected by bias (Ortner & Proyer, 2015). Therefore, it overcomes the main limitations of self-reports. Thirdly, the test registers data automatically and requires less resources and time than the observational methodology.

My Schedule was designed to assess time management in adults and is especially aimed at work and academic contexts. In both contexts, people have to make decisions about which tasks are most convenient to do at any given time.

Aim of the Study

The aim of this work is to study the validity and psychometric properties of My Schedule.

The first goal is to study reliability (internal consistency and test-retest). It is expected that separate trials within My Schedule will provide similar measures. In addition, it is expected that My Schedule will provide similar measures in two administrations separated by an interval of one month.

The second goal is to study convergent and divergent validity. When presenting a new instrument, is important to check convergence with a similar method that assesses a similar construct in addition to divergence with a similar method that assesses a different construct (e.g., DeVellis, 2016). Regarding convergent validity, we expect that My Schedule test will

show a positive relation with a test that also assesses time management behaviors: the Planning test (Santacreu, 2004a).

H1: Time management measures provided by My Schedule and the Planning test (Santacreu, 2004a) will be positively correlated.

Regarding divergent validity, it is expected that My Schedule test will not show a significant relation with an objective test that measures a different construct. We decided to administer My Schedule with a test that assesses risk-tendency: the Betting Dice test (Rubio & Santacreu, 1998). The scores of My Schedule should not show a relation with risk-tendency, that is, the tendency to choose options with higher value but lesser probability when any of the options has the same expected value (e.g., Arend et al., 2003). In My Schedule test, each activity provides different points, but the probability of achieving them does not play a role in the task.

H2: Time management measured by My Schedule will not show a significant correlation with risk-tendency measured by the Betting Dice test (Rubio & Santacreu, 1998).

The third goal is to evaluate the well-known lack of correspondence between objective tests and self-reports that purportedly measure the same underlying variable. The reason that several studies have not found a significant correlation between these methods is that what we say and what we do not necessarily stand in close correspondence (Ortner & Proyer, 2015; Santacreu & Hernández, 2017; Skinner & Howart, 1973). An objective test allows us to record time management behaviors, whereas a self-report obtains verbal descriptions of time management. They are therefore not necessarily measuring the same aspects of time management, and should not be interchangeable measures. We believe that it is important to compare results so that future practitioners who assess time management consider this information and make appropriate decisions about what measures they want to obtain (see Dang et al., 2020). We will employ the TMBQ (Macan et al., 1990) to assess

verbal descriptions of time management. TMBQ measures three dimensions of time management (establishing goals and priorities, time management tools, and perception of control over time) but none of them is expected to show a relation with Time management measured by My Schedule.

H3: Time management measured by My Schedule will not show a significant correlation with any of the time management dimensions of the TMBQ (Macan et al., 1990).

Method

Participants

One hundred and eight Psychology students (96 females and 12 males) of a Spanish University participated in the study. They received course credit as a reward for their participation. However, they also could get the course credit by doing a different activity.

Instruments

Time Management

My Schedule. This objective test was designed to assess time management behaviors based on behavioral decision-making theory (Koch & Kleinman, 2002). It is available upon request from the corresponding author.

PLEASE INSERT FIGURE 1

As described in the introduction, behavioral decision-making theory states that better time managers make optimal choices, that is, they complete tasks that offer higher values. Therefore, we decided to create a scenario in which participants could choose between different activities. Each activity provides a different number of points and takes a different amount of time to complete. My Schedule presents a schedule page with day hours (from 9 a.m. to 5 p.m.) and icons that represent activities: reading emails, answering calls, working on the computer, attending meetings, downloading documents and having a break (represented by a cup of coffee; see Figure 1). Each activity icon has an oval showing the points it

provides if completed. Under each activity, there is a bar that fills up when the activity is clicked, representing how much time it takes to complete.

The schedule page represents a day, with a bar moving from the top to the bottom of the schedule to represent time passing. Although the schedule presents hours from 9 a.m. to 5 p.m., the moving bar only reaches 2 p.m., representing that the work hours end at that time.

The schedule page has some hours highlighted. If an activity is completed in the unhighlighted hours, it offers the points indicated in the oval of the icon. However, if an activity is completed in the hour highlighted, it provides double the points. The schedule page presents highlighted hours from 9 a.m. to 5 p.m. However, as working hours are those from 9 a.m. to 2 p.m., participants would have to ignore the hours (highlighted or not) from 2 p.m.

Table 1 describes the value of each activity according to the rules that describe their contingency relations. The value of each activity is equal to the points divided by the time it takes to complete the activity. We assigned different values to the activities and established highlighted hours so that participants would have to make a decision on which activity to click and when. The differences in value encourage participants to manage their available time in order to achieve the highest number of points.

The test offers feedback about the moment an activity has been completed and how many points have been awarded. This feedback is represented by a circle placed in the schedule page.

PLEASE INSERT TABLE 1

The participants who best manage their time are those who make optimal decisions, that is, those who choose to click on the activity that offers the greatest value at a given time. They should click on the activities that initially provide the highest number of points so that they can be completed in the highlighted hours. As seen, participants have to take into account the points assigned to each task, the time the tasks take to complete and the

highlighted hours. The following are other factors to be considered to obtain higher numbers of points.

When participants are “working” on any activity, the other activities are not active, and participants cannot click on them except for “downloading documents”. Participants can click on “downloading documents” to complete it at the same time another activity is being completed and therefore to obtain more points than if they click on the activities consecutively. In addition, the “answering calls” icon activates every 5 seconds. If participants click on “answering calls” when another activity is being completed, it interrupts the activity, and therefore they do not obtain the points that could have provided. Then, optimal decisions include clicking on “downloading documents” so that it completes at the same time than other activities are being completed and ignoring “answering calls” if another activity is being completed.

The schedule shows a button that represents “having a break” (cup of coffee icon). Once clicked, the next task the participants choose will be completed in half the time. Hence, another optimal decision would be to click on “having a break” just before clicking a high-value activity that is close to the highlighted hours.

In sum, My Schedule was designed so that participants who show good time management behaviors would get a higher number of points. The activities that offer the highest values if completed in a specific time are “downloading documents”, “answering calls” (without interrupting other tasks), “attending meetings” and “working on the computer” (see the value column in Table 1). Therefore, optimal decisions are those directed to choose those activities in the proper time frame.

The test first presents instruction screens and then the trials (schedule pages). My Schedule has a total of 9 trials. The first trial is a training trial and lasts 120 seconds. Trials 2-9 are test trials and last 60 seconds each. The total duration is therefore 10 minutes; to which

should be added the time it takes participants to read the instructions (instructions can be read in less than 5 minutes).

My Schedule provides a Time management score based on the recorded data. The Time management variable is the mean number of points obtained in test trials (trials 2-9), with a response range between 0-300.

Planning Test (Santacreu, 2004a). In the Planning test, participants have to direct three moving dots so that they reach a funnel (Figure 2). Each dot in the screen moves at a different speed.

PLEASE INSERT FIGURE 2

Instructions state that the three dots must reach the funnel in the shortest possible time. In order to change the course of the dots, participants have to click on arrows located at the top of the screen (see Figure 2). The dots move at a constant speed through the “control area” of the top of the screen, and follow their initial course moving away from the funnel. If participants do not direct the dots when they are in the control area, they can disappear beyond the screen limits. They need to plan how to change the course of the dots so that none of them goes beyond the screen. In order to do the task efficiently, they need to make a choice about which of the three dots should change its course in the first place, taking into account the different speed at which dots move. Participants must change the course of each of the dots until, finally, all the dots go into the funnel in the shortest time possible. The time required to turn the three dots toward the funnel depends on the order in which the course of each of them is modified. So that all the points enter the funnel in the shortest possible time, the optimal decision is to guide the slowest dot first.

The Planning test is comprised of 3 training trials and 6 assessment trials. The maximum length of each trial is 25 seconds, but trials finish earlier if participants direct the

three dots toward the funnel and leave the control area or if they do not direct the dots in time and they disappear beyond the screen limits.

The variable provided by this test is calculated as follows (Santacreu, 2004b). Time management = mean of [total number of dots that a participant directs to the funnel in test trials + (number of dots that reach the funnel / total duration of the test trials)]. Duration is the time spent until the last dot leaves the control area. People who manage time efficiently would direct the slowest dot first. Therefore, the duration of the trial would be shorter and their score would be high. Response range is between 0-60.

Given the functional demands of the task, participants need a minimal level of spatial orientation aptitude to direct dots to the funnel. The spatial orientation criterion established in the task to obtain valid scores in the Time management variable was that the participant must be able to direct at least six dots to the funnel in the test trials. If a participant did not fulfill this criterion, we could not know whether he or she was unable to manage time efficiently or if he or she was unable to perform the task properly (Santacreu, 2004b). In this study, all participants fulfilled this criterion.

Test reliability of the Planning test reported by Santacreu (2004b) was 0.75. In the present work, Cronbach's alpha was 0.86.

Time Management Behavior Questionnaire (TMBQ) (Macan et al., 1990). We administered the Spanish version of TMBQ developed by García-Ros and Pérez-González (2012). This self-report has 34 items with a 5-point Likert scale. To measure Time management, the following scales should be employed (Macan et al., 1990):

1. Establishing goals and priorities: this scale assesses if participants tend to prioritize tasks. It is made up of 10 items and its values range between 10-50.

2. Time management tools: it assesses if participants tend to make a list of activities to do, if they check which activities are done, etc. It consists of 11 items with a response range between 11-55.

3. Preference for disorganization: this scale assesses whether participants tend to be disorganized and if they do not tend to plan their tasks. It is made up of 8 items. Its values are in the range between 8-40.

Reliability indexes reported by García-Ros and Pérez González (2012) were 0.84, 0.79 and 0.72 respectively. In the present work, reliability indexes (Cronbach's alpha) were 0.72, 0.75 and 0.61 respectively.

Risk-Tendency

Betting Dice Test (Rubio & Santacreu, 1998). The test instructions state that its aim is to make a bet about the result of rolling a pair of dice. If participants win the bet, they will get points. In each bet participants can choose one of four options (see Figure 3). The options refer to the result of adding the score obtained in both dice. For example, option 1 indicates that X points will be obtained if the sum of the result of the dice is a number less than or equal to 4.

PLEASE INSERT FIGURE 3

There are three Phases, and each of them has four trials. In Phase 1 the possible gains are 1, 2, 5 and 30 points while in Phase 3 the gains are 10, 20, 50 and 300 points. The high value of Phase 3 values with respect to Phase 1 usually increases the risk of the participants, although each of the options has the same expected value. In Phase 2 the possible gains are 1, 3, 8, 50, and the expected value of each option increases as the probability of hitting it decreases. In this Phase, the risk of the participants increases in comparison with Phase 1 due to the higher expected value of the riskier options.

The test shows two rolling dice while participants decide their bet. After making the bet, the test never shows feedback about the result. Participants who choose the first options are considered the least risk-takers. The test awards 1, 2, 3 or 4 points if they click on 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th option respectively. The Risk-tendency variable is the mean of scores obtained across trials. The response range is between 0-4.

The reliability index of the Betting Dice test observed in some studies varied between 0.69 – 0.85 (Arend et al., 2003; Rubio & Santacreu, 1998). In the present work the reliability index was 0.67.

Procedure

Data collection took place in two sessions separated by a time interval of one month. All participants signed an informed consent document to participate in the research. They were informed that their data would be anonymous. In Session 1, participants completed My Schedule, The Planning test, and Betting Dice on a computer and used a secure identification and password on an online server. Finally, they completed the TMBQ self-report. A month later, in Session 2 (re-test session), they completed My Schedule on a computer. At every moment, two psychologists supervised the test and self-report administration. Fortunately, there were no dropouts from Session 1 to Session 2, so the sample size remained the same. Attendance at both sessions was probably favored because participants had to attend both in order to obtain the course credit. Data analysis was performed using the SPSS 26 package.

Results

A test can only be reliable and provide precise assessments of a variable if the outcomes show variability. Therefore, we first checked the variability of the distribution of the Time management variable measured by My Schedule (Figure 4). It was normally distributed (Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test; $p > .05$)

PLEASE INSERT FIGURE 4

As said before, My Schedule was administrated in Session 1 ($M = 165.6$; $SD = 32.2$) and Session 2 (one month later) ($M = 197$; $SD = 32.1$). The increase between sessions was significant (paired samples t -test; $t(92) = -13.25$, $p < .001$) and could be attributable to the effects of the practice. To study reliability of the instrument, we calculated the values of Cronbachs' alpha coefficient for the test trials in Session 1 and 2 and the test-retest reliability. Cronbach's alpha of Time Management measured by My Schedule in Session 1 was 0.92 ($p < .001$) and 0.94 ($p < .001$) in Session 2. Test-retest reliability was high ($r = .71$; $p < .001$). Since the entire sample was exposed to the same test and therefore the same amount of practice, reliability does not seem to have been affected.

Next, we determined whether participants showed consistency throughout the My Schedule test by calculating interitem-variance (Baumeister & Tice, 1988). This procedure requires calculating the variance of the responses to the test trials for each participant. Then, we calculated the mean interitem-variance values and classified participants depending on whether they obtained values above or below the mean. Baumeister & Tice (1988) established the criterion that participants who showed values below the mean were labeled consistent. By using this procedure, 67% of the participants showed consistency.

Table 2 shows the correlations among the variables measured. My schedule showed moderate but significant convergence with the Planning test ($r = .31$; $p < .001$). On the other hand, Time management measured by My Schedule did not show a significant correlation with Risk-tendency (Betting Dice test) nor with any of the dimensions of the self-report (TMBQ).

PLEASE INSERT TABLE 2

Discussion

My Schedule test was designed to assess time management behaviors based on behavioral decision-making theory (Koch & Kleinman, 2002). People show time

management behaviors when they set one or more goals and when these goals require completing different tasks. They need to make decisions about which task to do and in which order so that they get the greatest benefits. Good time managers are those who choose and complete the most valuable tasks in a given time. The main goal of the present study was to determine the psychometric properties of My Schedule.

My Schedule appears to be a psychometrically sound measure. It showed high internal consistency and high test-retest reliability. The trials and the test and retest administration provided similar measures of time management. In addition, study participants also showed high consistency.

We checked convergent validity of My Schedule by administrating it with a test that also assesses time management behaviors: the Planning test (Santacreu, 2004a). The correlation value was moderate but significant (.31). Moderate convergence between objective tests has also been found in other studies. For example, regarding attention measures, Fernández-Marcos et al. (2018) studied convergence between the measures of three attention tasks. They found significant moderate correlations only between speed measures (values between .24 and .39) and global attention indexes (.37). Accuracy measures did not show significant correlations.

In our study, the time management behaviors specifically needed in My Schedule and the Planning test to obtain a high score are not equally important. My Schedule is complex and requires that the participant consider the time available in each trial. To obtain a high score, the participants have to make decisions about which tasks to complete first and initiate them so that they are completed at the time they provide the highest score. The Planning test requires the participant to analyze the position of the three dots moving away from the funnel. Then, they need to decide in which order to change the direction of the dots. The participants must ensure that the dots remain in the control area until they all have access to the funnel.

The duration of the trial is shorter if they manage their time efficiently (they should move the slowest dot first). My Schedule and the Planning test might not be assessing exactly the same time management behaviors, but they are obviously related overall. My Schedule might be more ecologically valid, as it was designed to represent a situation closer to what we all do in our work.

My Schedule also showed divergent validity. It assesses the decisions that participants make regarding which task to do, in which order and when, and these behaviors should not be related to taking risky decisions. Results showed that My Schedule objective test did not show a significant relation with an objective test that assesses risk-tendency (Betting Dice test; Arend et al., 2003; Rubio & Santacreu, 1998).

Another goal was to check if the designed objective test and a self-report that assesses time management are not related and therefore should be considered complementary instead of interchangeable measures. Our results show an absence of significant relation between My Schedule and the dimensions of the self-report (TMBQ; Macan et al., 1990). My Schedule is a complementary instrument to assess time management skills that offers a behavioral measure, and researchers should be aware of the fact that objective and subjective tests that purportedly measure the same variables might indeed be measuring different components of the same trait or skill.

Previous studies have found that, for at least some variables, there is a lack of correspondence between verbal descriptions and behavior (see Dang et al., 2020; Ortner & Proyer, 2015). Some researchers have pointed out that objective tests and self-reports might be assessing different aspects or levels of the same construct. In addition, objective tests that measure the same construct might be capturing different facets (e.g., Ortner & Proyer, 2015). It is clear that objective tests and self-reports differ in the way that they collect information of interest (Koch et al., 2014). Self-reports rely on one's own descriptions of behavior and

usually are measured on a Lickert scale. Objective tests rely on samples of behavior that people show when they face a specific situation and are usually administered on a computer.

From a theoretical point of view, we cannot assume that there is a correspondence between what we say (self-report) and what we do (objective tests). People's behavior at any given moment is the result of the accumulation and synthesis of experiences across a lifetime. It is possible to infer experience history from current behaviors and also from the language that people use to describe and analyze their behavior (Santacreu et al., 2002). Therefore, we are faced with a double synthesis: behavioral synthesis and verbal synthesis. These two types of syntheses do not always match. The flexibility of language also implies its possible inaccuracy. Moreover, social desirability can influence the direction of the verbal synthesis. For example, intelligence is a valuable ability in multiple contexts. People can tell themselves and others that they are intelligent, but we cannot assume that this verbal description will match their performance in a test that measures intelligence. That is why we do not assess intelligence by asking people. The same thing happens with other psychological variables, and there is no reason to think that it would be different in relation to time management.

The present study has implications for the theories and methodology used to investigate time management behavior. Researchers of time management have identified the need for objective measures of this construct (e.g., Jex & Elacqua, 1999; Macan, 1994). Our work is designed to address this need. My Schedule is an objective test with high reliability that complements data provided by other time management instruments. In addition, our study contributes to the time management literature by providing support for the application of the behavioral decision-making theory (Koch & Kleinman, 2002). My Schedule represents an ecologically valid situation in which multiple activities are to be completed under time constraints. The values of the activities differ depending on the time at which they are completed. Properly representing situations that require time management is one of the

important values of My Schedule. The development of objective assessment instruments is necessary to examine theoretical approaches to problems such as time management. To our knowledge, this is the first objective test designed explicitly on the basis of the behavioral decision-making theory, and it may contribute to expand the conceptual and methodological analyses of time management.

At a practical level, My Schedule is expected to be useful for practitioners who require an objective assessment of time management behaviors. The test only requires a computer to be executed. It takes about 15 minutes to complete and can be administered to individuals or groups assessed at the same time. My Schedule may be useful for companies and academic institutions that require an instrument to behaviorally assess time management without employing expensive and extensive temporal resources.

The main limitation of this study refers to the sample. My Schedule was administered to undergraduate Psychology students of a Spanish University and therefore cautious generalization of the results is warranted. My Schedule should be administered to larger samples with different characteristics and from different contexts (e.g., students of different branches of knowledge; a variety of samples of workers from different companies and countries, etc.), which would enable a more thorough analysis of its psychometric properties. We encourage other researchers to employ My Schedule in their studies in order to expand our knowledge and enrich the time management literature.

Declarations

Funding: The authors declare that there are no fundings to report

Conflicts of interest: The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Ethics approval: The study was approved by the research ethics committee of the Universidad Autonoma de Madrid (CEI-97-1787). All procedures performed in studies involving human participants were in accordance with the ethical standards of the institutional and/or national research committee and with the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its later amendments or comparable ethical standards.

Consent to participate: Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

Availability of data and material: The dataset analysed during the current study is available from the corresponding author.

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